

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEEPASHREE bearing USN 1SU19EC001 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Automatic Effluent Treatment for Coir Industry* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MADHURA S bearing USN 1SU19EC002 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Prepaid Payment for Utilities* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANASA G D bearing USN 1SU19EC003 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Analysis and Classification of Milk Quality Using Electronic Sensory Organs* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MERWIN NEIL KUTTIKAL** bearing **USN 1SU19EC004** has completed his/her minor project on ***“ IOT Based Smart Public Distribution System ”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAGASHRI bearing USN 1SU19EC005 has completed his/her minor project on “ *EEG Based Robot Control* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NOOTANKUMAR S MARISHETTI** bearing USN **1SU19EC006** has completed his/her minor project on “*Automated Human Activity Recognition in Video Surveillance System*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms POOJA bearing USN 1SU19EC007 has completed his/her minor project on “*E-Defense for Women Safety*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUMANTH P S bearing USN 1SU19EC008 has completed his/her minor project on *“Sequestering Machine”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUMUKH bearing USN 1SU19EC009 has completed his/her minor project on “*Smart Water Meter Using Wireless Networking*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHAYDEV SUNDAR V bearing USN 1SU19EC010 has completed his/her minor project on “*Electronic Car Ignitor*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYAN J R bearing USN 1SU19EC011 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Digital Watermarking Device* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYU A K** bearing **USN 1SU19EC012** has completed his/her minor project on ***“ Intelligent Car System for Accident Prevention Using ARM-7 ”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL S PRASAD** bearing **USN 1SU19EC013** has completed his/her minor project on ***“ Smartphone Controlled Quadcopter ”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY SHETTY** bearing **USN 1SU19EC014** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Plant to Reuse Water Using Sensor Technology”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAND C bearing USN 1SU19EC015 has completed his/her minor project on “ *The Smart Wrist Band Based Human Interface for PWD* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJALI UPADHYAYA bearing USN 1SU19EC016 has completed his/her minor project on “*Smart Pulmonary Function Analyser*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHIN RAJEEV bearing USN 1SU19EC017 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Smart School Van Safety System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AUSTIN PINTO bearing USN 1SU19EC018 has completed his/her minor project on *“Solar Powered Smart Agriculture System”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DELVY AUSTIN FERNANDES bearing USN 1SU19EC019 has completed his/her minor project on “*Smart Safety Jacket for Small Baby*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYA SOMAPPA LAMANI** bearing **USN 1SU19EC020** has completed his/her minor project on “*Smart Pill Box*” in the first Semester of the **Electronics & Communication Engineering** programme for the academic year **2019 - 20**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRITWHIK K** bearing **USN 1SU19EC021** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Artificial Intelligence Dietitian Using Android* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHAN M S** bearing **USN 1SU19EC022** has completed his/her minor project on “*ARM Based Smart Power Saving System for Home Automation*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NAVEEN KRISHNA K V** bearing **USN 1SU19EC023** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Android Interface based GSM Home Security System”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDHISHA ALVA** bearing **USN 1SU19EC024** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Advance Energy Management Using GSM Technology* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET